

The Development of Composite Materials in the People's Republic of China

K. Yuchang

Harbin FRP Research Institute, Harbin, China

In China, FRP industry began in 1958 and now the FRP has been widely used in industrial departments.

In early periods, FRP was used as insulation materials (such as sheetings and pipes) in electrical machinery and electrical equipment.

In early 60s, FRP began to be used as ablative materials, thus, drawing the attention from related departments.

In order to develop various FRP pressure vessels, the research work on filament winding technique was carried on in 1962. The helical winding pattern was concluded in 1964 and mechanical filament winding machines were designed and made, so that, various pressure vessels were wound. The hydraulic-servo-digital controlled filament winding machines were designed from then on.

FRP has been used to make various radomes. A 44 m diameter FRP honey-comb sandwich ground radome has been designed, fabricated and installed ten years ago.

FRP has been used in making blades of various types. These blades are widely used in cooling tower, wind tunnel etc., owing to its inherent properties, such as light weight, high damping, anticorrosive, easy process, reliability service and convenient maintenance.

In 1966, Changzhou Building Material Plant introduced a complete production technique and production equipment of unsaturated polyester resin from Scott Bader Co. in England. This plant becomes the main resin plant of unsaturated

polyester resins in China.

In recent ten years, FRP has been widely used in the petroleum chemical industry. The products include pipes, storage tanks, containers, valves, pumps, trough and lining etc.. The FRP pipes are in a large quantity and the FRP lining is widely used in anticorrosion products.

FRP has been used in marine engineering. The first RP yacht in China was made in 1958 and the largest FRP ship was made later on, it was 39 meters in length and 6 meters in width.

Now some vehicle parts are made of RP. The work of making vehicle parts could be easily done by the ordinary workers instead of the highly skilled worker. Thus the working wages can be saved and the products are cheap.

Transparent or semitransparent corrugated sheet, bath-tub, movable house, greenhouse and cooling tower etc. are also made of RP.

Generally speaking, the utilization of RP is in wide scale, but the quantity is not large enough, the annual output is only several ten thousand tons. According to the rough estimate of the Ministry of Building Materials Industry, FRP products are about 15,000 tons (exclusion insulation materials) in 1981 in China. This is mainly because the capacity of glass fiber and resin etc. are small, cost of resin and fiber are high, RP still meets difficulties in the competition with other traditional materials.

In recent years, the research work on expanding RP for civil use has been carried on improving products quality and decreasing its cost.

Glass fiber industry in China started from producing insulation materials. Glass fiber and its products are mainly the thin cloth with fine yarn, only a few of them are used for GRP. Later, roving, chopped strand mat, surface mat, roving cloth and the relative coupling agent have been developed.

For research work on resin, in addition to polyester, phenolic and epoxy resins, we have developed some cheap resin as well as reinforced thermalplastics.

For fabricating technology, in addition to hand lay-up and matched-die molding, we have developed preimpregnated technique (such as SMC and DMC), filament winding, continuous pipe making and pultrusion method. We have done much work on fabricating technology and stressed on its equipments. Thus, a good foundation was laid in developing the FRP industry.

For design and test of the products, we have carried on the research work on standardization of testing method; features of basic materials; quality control and testing method of products. We have already accumulated some experiences in products design and structural design. According to the characteristics of FRP and composite mechanics, we are making a new way in products design. We

concentrate our effort on technical and economical indices and have made certain achievements in connecting the theory with practice.

As structural uses, GRP provides high strength, but low modulus of elasticity, limiting its uses to high performance structure products. Some industrial departments urgently need advanced structural materials with light weight and high performance. So the research work on high performance composites and reinforcements have been carrying on. Since early 60s, we have started the research work on carbon fiber. After 1975, the research work on carbon fiber had moved into industrialized production. The carbon fiber composites were also developed. In late 70s, the research work on properties of composite materials made of aromatic polyamide fiber has been carrying on.

After carbon fiber, aromatic polyamide fiber and their composites appeared, their potentialities of industrial application have shown, and they lead to the related industrial departments' attention. Then the development of composite materials has come into a new stage. The related research institutes in China had paid much more attention on the development of carbon fiber and glass fiber hybrid reinforced composite materials.

Comparing with some advanced industrial countries, the development of composite materials in China still has a long way to go, we should make much effort on it in the future.

The researches on FRP have been carrying on in Nanjing Glass Fiber Research and design institute and FRP Research Institute in Beijing, Shanghai and Harbin. All these research organizations are working under the leadership of the Ministry of Building Materials Industry.

Nanjing Institute makes research work on production technology of glass fiber, develops new varieties of glass fiber and textile fabric.

The research work of FRP Research Institute includes the following subjects:

- 1) fabricating technology and its equipments;
- 2) basic properties of FRP and its test method;
- 3) method of structural design;
- 4) modification of resins;
- 5) quality control;
- 6) joint design and fastening method.

In China, many scientists from chemical industry, machines manufacturing, aircraft industry, ship building industry etc. are also doing the research work on FRP.

In order to strengthen academic exchange, a FRP Sub-committee of the Chinese

Silicate Society was founded in 1979. Academic conference organized by FRP Committee is held every two years.

In recent two years, main achievements gained are as follows:

- 1) blades of wind mill with vertical axis and with horizontal axis are made of GRP;
- 2) GRP cooling towers are produced;
- 3) various kinds of GRP pipe lines and tanks are used in industry;
- 4) Scanning electron microscope, x-ray diffractometer etc. have been used on the research work for basic properties of composites, the acoustic emission and laser hologram have been tried.
- 5) using the CAD method in structural design.

In 1980, we organized a FRP Sub-committee of Standardization. It has approved more than 20 items of standard of FRP property test.

In China, FRP Composites have attracted the leader of research institutes, colleges and industrial departments. The application of composites in industrial departments has expanded widely. Composites in China has a bright future.